

ANALYSIS AND OPTIMAL DESIGN OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

To fully explore the inherent high specific strength and high specific stiffness of the composite materials, and to realize the possibility of "tailoring" composite structures for particular design requirements, a large scale Composite structural Analysis and Synthesis System (COMPASS) is being developed, in order to improve aircraft performance and shorten its developing period. Based on a successful "Aircraft Multi-constraints Optimal Design System" (YIDOYU-1), its prototype reference system (called YIDOYU-1x) has been developed first. In this paper, preliminary numerical experience gained are given, and analytical capability and the feasibility of "structural tailoring" are demonstrated. It is proven to be a satisfactory way for the development of the practical engineering system.

1. INTRODUCTION

The developments in computer science have resulted in great contribution to the continuously improvement in the finite element techniques and the mathematical programming techniques; the sensible utilization of these advanced techniques has made structural optimization design techniques not only a topic of theoretical interest but a powerful tool for practical design. On the other hand, the high specific strength and high specific stiffness of composite materials, especially the possibility of "design" the material make it possible to further improve aircraft performance and reduce its structural weight dramatically. To consider the contrary aircraft design requirements, to improve design quality, and to speed up the development of new aircraft, the analysis and optimal design of composite structures have been an area of common interest(1,2).

As an effort in this direction, the development of a "Composite structural Analysis and Synthesis System (COMPASS)" (3), a computer software which uses finite element for analysis and mathematical programming for optimization, is now scheduled to make use of design-ability of composite materials. It can serve as a strength analysis and optimal design tool for composite structures and/or metallic-composite structures in the concept design and detailed design of aircraft development. It can also be used as an important sub-system of the aircraft CAD system.

To accelerate the development of the COMPASS, a prototype reference system YIDOYU-1x based on a successful aircraft multi-constraints optimal design system YIDOYU-1 has been developed. Its capabilities for structural analysis have been tested and the "structural tailoring" concept is studied. Several numerical examples, including the structural analysis of a cantilever box wing, a swept wing and a delta wing structure and including "structural tailoring", are given in this paper. The numerical results are satisfactory.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE COMPASS

A general overview of the COMPASS is shown in Fig.1. It includes following modules: Pre-and Post-processing, aerodynamic force and loads, structural modeling, structural analysis, optimization model, and optimization algorithms etc., an executive and a data management sub-system, the flexible implement of the system. The structural analysis module is at the kernel of the system, which can do static analysis (including stress, strain, and displacement under steady temperature load), dynamic analysis (natural frequency and mode), static-aeroelastic analysis (control efficiency, reversal speed, divergence speed of wing etc.) and flutter analysis (flutter speed of wing). In view of the special requirements in optimization process, the needs of structural reanalysis techniques, behaviour derivative calculations and data structure and programming technique are also considered in the choice of algorithms.

In the optimization module, besides the conventional design constraints on stress, strain, frequency, static aeroelastic and flutter speed, one main feature of COMPASS is to make use of the orthotropic characteristics and deformation coupling of composite materials, so that expected deformation under external loads could be resulted to improve its aerodynamic behaviors and structural responses. This designability of "aeroelastic tailoring" is the unique important feature of composite structures compared to the metallic structures. By changing design parameters such as the thickness and the direction of different laminate, optimum aerodynamic and/or structural behaviors and dynamic response of aircraft lift surface could be attained. For the practical implementation of this system, the aerodynamic calculation, the structural analysis and the optimization algorithms etc. will be involved. Because the existing YIDOYU-1 system has already had the fundamental functions demanded, a prototype reference system based on it has been developed to guide the development of the new system.

3. Basic functions of YIDOYU-1x

YIDOYU-1 is a multi-constrained optimization system for aircraft structures. In the case of given structural layout and materials, the optimum section sizes of elements and weight variables are selected to obtain a minimum structural design that satisfies the assigned constraints. The system utilizes mathematical programming techniques to optimize the structural design under a variety of constraints—stress, displacement, vibration frequency, flutter speed, static aeroelasticity (various efficiencies, divergence speed) and elements side constraints. The system also has following inherent functions: load calculations, steady and unsteady aerodynamic force calculations, displacement and stress analysis, flexibility coefficient calculation, natural vibration analysis, flutter analysis, static aeroelastic analysis, analytic derivative calculation and fully stressed design. Based on YIDOYU-1, some composite structural analysis and design functions are developed in the YIDOYU-1x system. The static and natural vibration analysis functions have been demonstrated first, and further development is being continued.

4. VERIFICATION OF THE YIDOYU-1x ANALYSIS FUNCTIONS

Structural analysis is the most fundamental part of the system. In order to verify the YIDOYU-1x analysis function for composite structures, several known typical examples are chosen.

(1) Cantilever box wing (6,7)

This wing box is a standard problem extremely used (Fig.2). Its right end is subjected to two types of concentrated loads (bending and twisting) as shown. In bending loads case $P_1=P_2=1,000$ lb, $P_3=P_4=1,000$ lb;

in the twisting load $P_1=P_2=1,000$ lb, $P_3=P_4=950$ lb. The structure is symmetric with respect to its two middle planes, the vertical webs are made of aluminum alloy. The skins are made of 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° boron-epoxy orthotropic laminates. The material properties are given in Table 1. The thickness of the metallic web panel is 0.1 in; the thickness of 90° , $\pm 45^\circ$ plies are all 0.004896 in; and the 0° ply thickness has 9 different levels increasing from right end to left end (Table 2). The skins width is 12 in.

Because the structure is symmetric, only the upper half is considered. It is therefore modeled by 36 orthotropic elements for skin panels and 18 symmetric shear panel elements for the vertical webs.

Displacement results of this wing by YIDOYU-1x are shown and compared with those from other literatures in Table 3 and 4. The first four natural frequencies are 233.2, 239.7, 763.2 and 780.7 rad/s respectively.

(2) Swept wing model (8)

The wing model is shown in Fig.3. There are three beams, eight ribs and 39 web column bars. The beams are between node points 9-79, 3-83, 7-87, the ribs are between node points 9-7, 9-17, 19-27, 29-37, 39-47, 49-57, 59-67, 69-77. The web column bars are allocated between each corresponding nodes at the intersections of ribs and wing surfaces.

All the beams, ribs and bars of the wing model are made of aluminum. The skin panels are made of $(0^\circ/90^\circ /45^\circ /-45^\circ)$ sym. graphite-epoxy orthotropic laminate panels. The 0° ply is coincided with the middle beam direction. Here, only the wing box between front beam 9-79 and rear beam 7-87 is considered, modeling with 39 metallic bar elements, 55 metallic shear elements and $4*64=256$ composite orthotropic membrane elements.

The displacement results obtained by YIDOYU-1x are shown in table 5.

(3) Delta wing model (9)

The delta wing consists of graphite-epoxy skins and titanium webs, which is symmetric with respect to the middle surface (x-z plane) as shown in Fig.4. The skin panel are made of 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° symmetrical graphite epoxy laminates. 0° ply is at the spanwise direction, and the 90° ply is at the chordwise direction. As the wing is symmetric, only the upper half of it (as same as example 1) is modeled using $4*63=252$ triangular orthotropic membrane elements for the skin and 70 symmetric shear panel elements for the vertical webs. The wing is subjected to a single static load condition corresponding to an uniformly normal distributed loading of 6.89 kn/m². Since the example in (9) is a comprehensive one which considered temperature load, and is optimized by dual method, only its initial design is chosen as initial design here in this paper.

The analysis results obtained by YIDOYU-1x are shown in table 6.

5. STUDY ON THE FEASIBILITY OF "AEROELASTIC TAILORING" CAPABILITY

Besides the general way of design optimization by adjusting the total thickness of laminate plate, the proportion of different plies of a symmetrical balanced laminates, there is another hopeful way of "tailoring" that is to change the orientation of a symmetrical balanced laminate to utilize the axial force-shear coupling of laminate, or to use the symmetric unbalanced laminate to utilize the twist force-twist deformation coupling of laminate. In this way, beneficial structural deformation under external loads may be expected to improve the aero-dynamic characteristics and response properties of structures. In this paper, these two possibilities of "structural tailoring" are studied by several nume-

rical examples.

In the cantilever box example shown in Fig.2, we change the laminate orientatino angles and the thickness of 45° ply to explore "structural tailoring". The load condition is same as pure bending case in Fig.2. The procedure is : successively increase a $\Delta\theta$ to 0° ply, thus the sectional bending-twist coupling of the cantilever box is resulted, which therefore changes the aerodynamic behaviors of this box wing. The twist angles are shown in Fig.5. Next step, change the thickness of $\pm 45^{\circ}$ ply, which also causes twist behavior change of the box and realize "aeroelastic tailoring".

6. CONCLUDING

From above discussion in section 4-5, it can be concluded that:

1. The results from YIDOYU-1x are consistent with those from other literatures, which proves the validity of the elements used and of the program implementation.
2. YIDOYU-1x may be used to analysis composite structures. And the system possesses a strong Pre- and Post-processing capability, easy to use.
3. The self-orthotropic behaviors and tension-shear, tension-bending and bending-twist coupling behaviors of composite laminates can be used to realize "aeroelastic tailoring" which may be obtained by adjusting the orientation angles of ply and/or thickness of laminates.
4. The prototype reference system YIDOYU-1x could supply a good tool to develop COMPASS system. Based on it, other functions may be further developed and benefits are got rapidly.

REFERENCES

1. D.J.Neill etc., "ASTROS - A Multidisciplinary Automated Structural Design tool", AIAA 87-0713, 1987.
2. D.Keppeler etc., "Weight Optimization of Composite Light Weight Structures Using MBB-Lugrange", 1986.
3. Ding Huiliang, "Composite structural Analysis and Synthesis System (COMPASS), Project developing plan", CAE, 1988.1.
4. Ye Kejia etc., "YIDOYU-1: Computer system for Optimal Wing Design", N84-10768.
5. Wang Wen etc., "A Large Scale Composite Structural Analysis and Optimization System YIDIYU-1x User's manual", CAE, 1986.9.
6. N.S.Khot etc., "Optimum Design of Composite Structure with Stress and Displacement Constraints", AIAA Paper 75-141.
7. "Finite Element Analysis Testing Examples of Metallic-Composite Structure", Nanjing Aeronautical Institute, China.
8. N.S.Khot etc., "Optimum Design of Composite Wing Structures with Twist Constraint for Aeroelastic Tailoring", AFFDL-TR-76-117.
9. C.FLEURY etc., "Dual Methods and Approximation Concepts in Structural Synthesis", NASA CR-3226, 1980.

Table 1. Material properties of cantilever box wing

		skin	webs
Material :		Boron-epoxy	Aluminum
Young's moduli :		$E_1=30.0 \times 10^6$ psi	$E=10.5 \times 10^6$ psi
		$E_t=2.7 \times 10^6$ psi	
Shear modulus :		$G_{1t}=0.7 \times 10^6$ psi	
Poisson's ratio :		$\nu_{t1}=0.0189$	$\nu=0.3$

Table 2. The thickness of 0° ply (from left to right, unit=in)

pure bending	0.08710	0.07824	0.06741	0.05666	0.04588	0.03551	0.02439
bending twist	0.08710	0.07834	0.06752	0.05676	0.04572	0.03517	0.02443

0.01361	0.004896
0.01363	0.004805

Table 3. The nodes' deflections in Z-direction under pure bending loads

node	1-4	5-8	9-12	13-16	17-20	21-24	25-28	29-32	33-36
(6)	17.81	14.29	11.12	8.34	5.96	3.98	2.39	1.19	0.39
(7)	17.804	14.291	11.12	8.34	5.96	3.98	2.39	1.195	0.399
pres.	17.803	14.291	11.12	8.341	5.962	3.978	2.389	1.196	0.399

Table 4. The nodes' deflections in Z-direction under bending-twist loads

node	1-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10	11-12	13-14	15-16	17-18
(6)	17.97	17.14	14.42	13.76	11.22	10.71	8.42	8.04	6.01
(7)	17.79	17.38	14.28	13.95	11.11	10.85	8.34	8.141	5.96
pres.	17.76	17.36	14.26	13.93	11.10	10.84	8.328	8.132	5.951
node	19-20	21-22	23-24	25-26	27-28	29-30	31-32	33-34	35-36
(6)	5.74	4.01	3.83	2.40	2.30	1.20	1.15	0.40	0.38
(7)	5.82	3.98	3.88	2.39	2.33	1.20	1.17	0.40	0.39
pres.	5.810	3.976	3.875	2.384	2.327	1.194	1.165	0.3782	0.3886

Table 5. Deflections at tip of swept wing

node deflec.	7			9			web twist (deg.)
	X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z	
(8)	-0.0565	13.4306	-0.1961	-0.0435	10.6296	-0.1632	-5.4583
(9)	-0.0815	13.830	-0.2074	-0.0459	10.574	-0.1608	-6.373
pres.	-0.05205	13.2633	-0.1926	-0.0406	10.5273	-0.1611	-5.344

Table 6. Transverse deflections of delta wing

node	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
deflec.	25.150	29.195	12.684	16.098	19.694	8.819	9.632
node	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
deflec.	11.38	13.635	6.620	7.641	7.079	7.778	9.071
node	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
deflec.	4.791	5.691	5.840	4.992	5.050	5.808	2.860
node	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
deflec.	3.367	4.216	4.050	3.107	2.842	3.250	1.207
node	29	30	31	32	33	34	35
deflec.	1.781	2.181	2.362	2.184	1.444	1.159	1.339

Figure 1. The overview of COMPASS

Fig. 2. Analytic model of cantilever box wing

Fig.3. Analytic model of swept wing

Fig. 4. Analytic model of delta

Fig. 5. The sectional twist by changing the orientation angle of 0° ply

Fig.6. The sectional twist by changing the thickness of 45° ply